

POLYPHEM

Small-Scale Solar Thermal Combined Cycle

D3.1 Report on the designs and specifications of filler, tank and foundations

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The POLYPHEM project is a research and innovation action funded by the European Union's H2020 program. It is implemented by a European consortium of 4 research centres and 5 industrial partners. The aim is to increase the flexibility and improve the performance of small solar tower power plants. The concept of POLYPHEM consists in implementing a combined cycle formed by a solarized micro gas-turbine and a Rankine organic cycle machine, with an integrated thermal storage device between the two cycles. The need for cooling is minimal.

Developed from a patented technology by CNRS and CEA, the pressurized air solar receiver is integrated in the micro-turbine cycle. The thermal efficiency targeted for the receiver is 80% with a cost of 400 €/kW. The innovative thermal storage uses thermal oil and a single thermocline tank with a technical concrete filler material.

The main expected impact of this project is to enhance the competitiveness of low-carbon energy production systems through the technology developed. The expected progress is a better fitting of electricity generation to variable local needs, an overall conversion efficiency of solar energy into electricity of 18% for an investment cost of less than 5 €/W and a low environmental impact. By 2030, the cost of electricity production targeted by the POLYPHEM technology is 165 €/MWh for an annual direct normal irradiation of 2600 kWh/m²/year (North Africa and Middle East) and 209 €/MWh under 2050 kWh/m²/year (Southern Europe). In addition to decentralized power generation, other applications are considered for the deployment of this technology used in poly-generation: industrial heat production, solar heating and cooling, desalination of seawater or brackish water.

A prototype plant of 60 kW_{el} with a thermal storage of 1300 kWh is designed, built and installed on the site of the experimental solar tower of Themis in Targasonne (France). The objective of the project is to validate the technical choices under test conditions representative of actual operating conditions.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/abbreviation	Meaning/full text
AALB	Aalborg CSP
ARRA	Arraela S.L.
CA	Consortium Agreement
CEA	Commissariat à l’Energie Atomique
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CIEMAT	Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
CO	Confidential: only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
C_p	Specific heat capacity
CSP	Concentrated Solar Power
D	Deliverable
ETC	Effective Thermal Conductivity
EU	European Union
EURO	Euronovia
FEM	Finite Element Model
FISE	Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems, ISE
HTF	Heat Transfer Fluid
KAE	Kaefer Isoliertechnik GmbH
M	Month
MS	Milestone
ORC	‘Orcan Energy AG’ or ‘Organic Rankine Cycle’
PU	Public
STE	Solar Thermal Electricity (equivalent to Concentrated Solar Power)
TES	Thermal Energy Storage
WP	Work Package

1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable presents not only the designs and specifications of filler, tank and foundations but also the required studies, experimental results and the testing devices developed for obtaining some of them.

Figure 1: TES system is the bridge between the two thermodynamic cycles in the Polyphem prototype plant

A unique tank where both cold and hot media stay was, from the project proposal, the chosen option as thermal energy storage (TES) solution. A thermocline system with a solid filler and thermal oil as Heat Transfer Fluid (HTF) will be erected. The approach is to implement a non-pressurized tank made of concrete and to promote the utilization of concrete for insulating foundation. These approaches are expected to be effective solutions for solving the limitation in size imposed by metallic storage tanks and expanded clay aggregate (Arlita® Leca®) spheres as insulation for foundation.

The useful capacity of the TES unit of the prototype plant will be 2 MWh.

This report is structured by first presenting what materials, both solid -for tank walls and filler-, and liquid -for HTF-, are under consideration. The protocol and autoclave for testing compatibility between materials follows. The thermo-structural properties relevant for this specific application as part of a thermal storage system are shown and the process and facilities to measure them are described whenever there is not a standard protocol for such a characterization. The report ends with a structural analysis which defines the required thicknesses, reinforcement and inlet/outlet designs.

2. MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION

The main materials involved in the storage system are a heat transfer fluid (HTF), solid filler, a concrete formulation for the tank walls and a concrete formulation for the tank foundations.

For the selection of all the materials it is necessary to consider that:

- All of them have to be stable under the expected working conditions of the Polyphem approach (i.e. in the case of the storage loop, the working temperature is within the range 100-330°C),
- All the materials have to be compatible between each other, i.e., to show no degradation because of being in contact with others and their properties (mainly structural and thermal) do not change.
- Each material has to fulfil the purpose what it is in the storage system for, i.e., concrete formulations for tank walls and foundations should have an adequate structural behaviour, concrete foundations should be a good thermal insulator, solid filler and HTF should have an elevated heat capacity.

As HTF, Jarysol® oil (also called Jarytherm DBT) has been chosen since it does not require any over pressure in the temperature working range (see Table 1) and it has been used as HTF in other STE facilities without any declared problem [1]

Table 1: Thermophysical properties and characteristics of Jarysol® thermal oil (see ANNEX 1).

TYPICAL PROPERTIES	METHODS	UNITS	JARYTHERM® DBT			
			20 °C	100 °C	200 °C	300 °C
Density	ISO 3675	kg/m ³	1043	987	914	834
Kinematic viscosity	ISO 3104	mm ² /s	50	3	0.82	0.44
Specific heat capacity	-	kJ/kg °C	1.60	1.81	2.10	2.51
Thermal conductivity	-	W/m °C	0.128	0.121	0.113	0.105

Above characteristics are mean values given as an information.

TYPICAL CHARACTERISTICS	METHODS	UNITS	JARYTHERM® DBT
Flash point OC	ISO 2592	°C	200
Fire point	ISO 2592	°C	230
Pour point	ISO 3016	°C	- 34
Boiling point (under 760 mm of mercury)	-	°C	390
Total Decomposition Rate – 1000h, 350°C.	GB23800-2009	%	6.9
Operating range	-		
- in the bulk		°C	0 / + 350
- in the film		°C	370

Above characteristics are mean values given as an information.
A few useful conversion factors:

Several materials have been considered for tank walls, insulating foundation and filler:

- **HEATEK-AC:** concrete formulation created on purpose for Polyphem project with **natural granular material**, with a large content of magnetite and FeO.
- **HEATEK-RC:** concrete formulation created on purpose for Polyphem project with **urban wastes** (non-metallic) as granular material.
- **HEATEK-RV:** concrete formulation created on purpose for Polyphem project with **metallic slags** from industrial blast furnaces as granular material.
- **Volcanic lava:** natural igneous **rocks**.

Volcanic lava was disregarded from the very beginning, since there are just a few places where to find it: Cape Verde and Canary Island. The logistics of bringing it from Cape Verde is expensive and difficult, because the port in Fogo currently is not good enough equipped. There is no option of acquiring the material from the Canary Islands, since it is found in a Natural Reserve.

In order to see which one of these three first materials is the most suited for each application, they all have been submitted to tests with Jarytherm DBT oil and characterized, before and after testing, in terms of composition, density, heat capacity, thermal conductivity, and mechanical behaviour.

2.1 TESTING FOR LONG TERM PERFORMANCE

In order to evaluate and predict as much as possible the feasibility and long-term performance of the materials to be used in the storage system, oil/concrete compatibility tests have been performed. Since there is no standard protocol related, discussions between the partners involved (CIEMAT, CEA and Arraela) have risen up that for extrapolating the results obtained in a short time:

- It is important to follow a similar thermal scheme as the material will have in real operation, so both thermal cycles between minimum and maximum working temperatures and stand-by periods at the highest working temperature will be considered.
- According to previous experiences with Jarytherm DBT oil (CEA) and in order to compare with Jarytherm DBT data sheet (Annex 1) where it is claimed that it has successfully passed Thermal Stability tests of ASTM D6743, DIN 51528, GB/T 23800-2009, for 1000h at 350°C, a testing period of 1000h (42 days, i.e. 42 cycles at rate 1 cycle/24h) has been established.
- Reproducibility is a must in order to have reliable results. Due to the time limitation for this testing in the project, three samples of the same material will be tested at the same time and all of them characterized afterwards.
- Concrete is a heterogeneous material so a minimum sample size is required. Mainly for the post-testing structural analysis samples of a minimum of 10x10x10 cm³ are required; therefore, this is the elected sample size.

There are not specific success/failure criteria to assure that any of the considered materials will withstand working conditions for a long term, but more a qualitative analysis of the change of their properties after following the tests protocol defined in the next paragraph.

2.1.1 Tests protocol

Although many tests could be performed, due to the boundary time schedule of the project, the test procedure was agreed to be the following:

- Samples of oil and solid materials are characterized prior to testing.
- The relative atmosphere in the autoclave is kept under N_2 @ 2 bar and automatically regulated (according to Jarytherm DBT data sheet –Annex 1-, it should work under Nitrogen atmosphere to prevent degradation by oxidation).
- Daily heating/cooling cycles are performed in the temperature interval: 100-330°C, with a heating time of 5h, cooling time of 15 h and stand-by time of 2 hours at each minimum and maximum temperature.
- The test-cell is heated up using electrical resistors and it is cooled down from the bottom using water flow.
- Test duration is about 1000 hours (42 days).
- Solid materials and oil are characterized after testing.

2.1.2 Experimental device: autoclave

After discussing and even manufacturing several different designs of the device to test concrete samples in contact with Jarysol[®] oil according to the above protocol, the final device has the following description.

Figure 2: Scheme of autoclave for performing compatibility tests oil-concrete formulations

2.1.3 Test Campaign

The three grades of concrete materials have been tested according to the above protocol in the following dates:

HEATEK-RC: from 02/01/2019 to 13/02/2019

HEATEK-AC: from 19/02/2019 to 04/04/2019

HEATEK-RV: from 08/04/2019 to 19/05/2019

As an example, the experimental temperature data of HEATEK-RC is shown in Figure 3:

Figure 3: Set of experimental campaign for HEATEK-RC and detail for the first two cycles

With this autoclave, around 5 hours are required to heat up the system up to 330°C and a little bit more to cool it down to 100°C. The sample is kept at 330°C for, at least, 2 hours. It is worth mentioning the temperature homogeneity is achieved in this autoclave as the oil 1 and oil 2 measuring points reveal.

The appearance of the samples after 42 days cycling shows an apparent impregnation of the oil in its surface (see Figure 4). Nevertheless radial saw cuts on each of the tested samples show that there is no major oil penetration into the internal part of the samples (see Figure 5).

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: Concrete samples (a) outside and (b) inside the device for long term performance testing

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5: (a) Cutting HEATEK-RC sample with a radial saw; (b) left and (c) right internal faces after cutting

2.2 ELEMENTARY COMPOSITION, DENSITY AND MECHANICAL RESISTANCE

The **mineralogical composition** of each of these solid materials has been measured by X-Ray by Bruker, subcontracted by Arraela. The results are shown in the tables of ANNEX 2. These results are consistent with the granular material used in each formulation: in the HEATEK-AC there is a great amount of Fe, while in HEATEK-RC SiO₂ is the dominant substance. HEATEK-RV shows large content of both CaO and SiO₂.

Density and mechanical resistance have been measured by CYE (Control y Estudios), subcontracted by Arraela. It has to be highlighted that being concrete a non-homogenous material, a deviation of 10% between samples can be expected for the values of density reported in Table 2. The reduction of mechanical resistance observed for HEATEK-AC (from 103.6 MPa to 72.5 MPa) and HEATEK-RV (from 110 MPa to 87.7 MPa) are in accordance with the proposals of Aslani and Samali [2, 3, 4] for concrete materials subjected to high temperature. The decrease is much larger for HEATEK-RC (from 61.5 MPa to 17.9 MPa) but its mechanical resistance is still high enough to avoid expecting any structural failure.

Another way of testing the mechanical behaviour of the samples was to cut them with a radial saw (see previous paragraph). For all the samples, no cracking was observed after the cut, which denotes a very good structural behaviour.

Table 2: Density and mechanical characteristics of concrete samples

	Before/After testing	Density (kg/m ³)	Mechanical Resistance (MPa)
		Before/After testing	Before/After testing
HEATEK-AC		3925/3980	103.6/72.5
HEATEK-RC		2040/2145	61.5/17.9
HEATEK-RV		3160/3105	110.0/ 87.7

2.3 HEAT CAPACITY

The experimental characterization of the Cp of all the solid samples has been done by the X-Ray Unit of the University of Santiago de Compostela (A Coruña), subcontracted by Arraela. Temperature Modulated Differential Scanning Calorimetry (TMDSC or ADSC) has been used for obtaining the heat capacity of all these solids since it supplies the most reliable results. With this method, the temperature is varied as a sine function of time and is superimposed on the average heating rate. In this specific case, starting from a sample at thermal equilibrium at 50°C, the temperature is $\pm 1.59^\circ\text{C}$ modulated every 60s, superimposing a $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ heating rate up to 400°C .

The results are shown in the following Table 3 and depicted in Figure 6.

Table 3: Heat capacity (in kJ/kg.K) of the different concrete grades (Modulated method, in N₂) as it appears in Figure 7)

	100°C	150°C	200°C	250°C	300 °C
HEATEK-AC	1.2	1.25	1.6	2.25	1.75
HEATEK-RC	2.6	2.6	1.9	1.9	1.7
HEATEK-RV	0.75	0.85	0.95	1.1	1.25

Taking into account the composition of HEATEK–RV and HEATEK-RC it was expected that the Cp of the first one was higher than the second one, which is not the case, according to the experimental results given by the University of Santiago. This is the reason why the granular material used in HEATEK-RV formulation (e.g. metallic slags) was sent to be measured. The results are shown in Figure 7 (bottom right). The Cp values obtained with the modulated method for this sample of granular material (grey full line) are a little bit higher than the HEATEK-RV ones: between 1.25 kJ/kg·K at 100°C up to 1.95 kJ/kg·K, which is very consistent with the corresponding concrete results.

Figure 6: Heat capacity measurements of sapphire material reference and disregarded volcanic lava

HEATEK-AC

HEATEK-RC

HEATEK-RV

Figure 7: Heat capacity of concretes measured with different approaches.

2.4 THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY

Thermal conductivity is the intrinsic ability of a material to transfer or conduct the heat. Hence it is one of the most interesting properties to study.

The method used for measuring thermal conductivity of the concretes here considered is the same as the one already developed and used by Ciemat when measuring insulating materials under compression. Since one of these concretes will be used as foundation material it seems to be a good approach to use the same technique. Storage tank foundations in solar thermal concentrating solar power plants (STE) are insulated from the tank itself by means of a porous aggregate layer (Arlita®), in order to avoid damaging the mechanical properties of the concrete structure that normally does not stand temperatures above 400°C. The physical properties of this insulating material change because of the pores size reduction caused by the material pre-consolidation and the weight of the filled tank. Prior to the energy storage tank placement, Arlita® has the properties listed in Table 4 and it is pre-compressed, until it reaches a density of 500 kg/m³.

Table 4: Arlita® Leca Solar (4-20 mm): Thermo-mechanical properties [5]

Symbol	Property	Value	Units
ε	Porosity	0.55	-
ρ_b	Bulk density	290	kg m ⁻³
ρ_p	Particle density	784	kg m ⁻³
E_r	Crushing resistance	> 0.80	MPa
T_{mp}	Melting point	1200	°C
C_p	Specific heat capacity	1161 (39 °C)	J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
		1433 (198 °C)	J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
		1646 (398 °C)	J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
λ	Thermal conductivity	0.125 (39 °C)	W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
		0.165 (198 °C)	W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
		0.325 (398°C)	W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹

This method, and the used device, is based on steady state hot plate technique with guardian method. The hot plate method is a steady state technique, the most usually used for the material in consideration; despite it has some drawbacks (long time required to reach steady state conditions, larger sample sizes compared to other techniques and set-up complexity), it is commonly used because of the good accuracy of the results.

2.4.1 Set-Up and Procedure

The used device is the same as the one Ciemat has for measuring the effective thermal conductivity (λ) of a pebble bed made of solid porous material, like expanded clay aggregate (Arlita® Leca Solar) is when it is subjected to different compressive mechanical stresses. It is based on the hot plate method.

Among the different possible approaches a vertical uni-axial load, from the top to the bottom, has been chosen, in agreement with other devices found in literature [6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11]. In the same way as in R. Lo Fano et al., [6], the compression in the device is obtained by using a hydraulic press. A vertical temperature gradient is achieved, as in Widenfeld et al., [7], by using an electric resistance at the top and a cooling circuit at the bottom. Additionally, the device is insulated with fiberglass in order to avoid as much heat losses as possible.

When measuring material that may change its properties when compressed, the first step is to compact it at a specific pressure level. Afterwards, the top cover with the electric heater plate is placed, adjusting its position by means of a screw and a rafter, and insulating the whole device. The pump provides a constant mass flow rate of 0.3 kg/s of the cooling water.

While the heater and cooling system are on, the sample is warmed up until the steady state condition is reached. Several thermocouples measure the temperature along the central vertical axis. A control system connected to the electrical heater regulates the temperature in order to keep constant the temperature of the upper plate. A data acquisition system completes the set-up.

The device is composed by seven components, observable in detail in Figure 8. They are:

1. Case
2. Top cover, transmitting the pressure from the piston;
3. Top electric heater
4. Handle, to place and remove the electric heater;
5. Cooling circuit at the bottom
6. Positioning rafter, which is used as support for the height adjuster;
7. Height adjuster, to establish the heater at the exact height after the compression.

Figure 8: Thermal conductivity device scheme and picture

A 0.5 m³ tank provides water to the cooling circuit at the bottom of the device. The amount of water inside the tank, kept at external ambient temperature, is large enough to avoid a significant temperature increase, because the returning hot water is not more than 10°C above ambient temperature. There is a valve downstream, needed to regulate the mass flow rate at the constant value of 0.3 kg/s (see Figure 9).

Figure 9: Experimental set-up layout

Figure 10: Grooves for inserting thermocouples in concrete sample of 10x10x10 cm³

For the case of concrete samples, no previous compression was applied. The thermocouples were positioned only above and below the concrete sample; three thermocouples at each side, inserted into grooves which ends at 90 mm, 50 mm, 25 mm from the edge. The grooves are separated 5 mm from each other. See Figure 10 for a better clarification. Similar grooves were made on the opposite side so that the thermocouples are in the same vertical position.

Once the steady state condition is achieved, the evaluation of the λ of the sample can be performed according to the equation

$$\lambda = \Phi_{net} \frac{\Delta z_{tc}}{\Delta T_{tc}} \quad \text{eq. 1}$$

where λ is the effective thermal conductivity of the material, Φ_{net} is the net heat power across the sample bed; ΔT_{tc} is the temperature difference measured by two thermocouples at different heights; and Δz_{tc} is the distance between two different thermocouples positions along the central vertical axis.

The net heat flux is obtained by considering the effective power generated by the resistance Φ_{eff} (the nominal power multiplied by the time it is switched on) and by subtracting the conductive, Φ_{cond} and convective Φ_{conv} heat loss across the envelope at the correspondent height.

$$\Phi_{net} = \Phi_{eff} - \Phi_{cond} - \Phi_{conv} \quad \text{eq. 2}$$

$$\Phi_{eff} = \frac{\Delta T_{ss}}{\frac{\Delta z_{ss}}{k_{ss}} + \frac{\Delta z_{sample}}{k_{sample}}} \quad \text{eq. 3}$$

where:

ΔT_{ss} is the temperature difference across the stainless steel plate;

Δz_{ss} is the thickness of the stainless steel plate;

$\frac{\Delta z_{sample}}{k_{sample}}$ is a corrective term due to the imperfect contact between thermocouple placed bellow the top cover with electrical heater (3 in Figure 8) and the plate; because of it, the sensor of the thermocouple could stay from one to 2mm lower than the plate.

Conductive heat losses are evaluated by integrating the infinitesimal losses along the height of the device, starting from the top, until reaching the coordinate of the considered thermocouple.

$$\Phi_{\text{cond}} = \frac{1}{(H_{\text{sample}} - H_{\text{th}})} \int_{H_{\text{th}}}^{H_{\text{sample}}} \frac{1}{\frac{t_{\text{SS}}}{k_{\text{SS}}} + \frac{t_{\text{fg}}}{k_{\text{fg}}}} \Delta T_{\text{env}} dh \quad \text{eq. 4}$$

where:

- H_{th} is the vertical position of the thermocouple;
- H_{sample} is the height of the sample;
- t_{SS} is the thickness of the stainless steel wall;
- t_{fg} is the thickness of the fiberglass layers;
- ΔT_{env} is the measured temperature difference across the double-layer wall;

Convective heat losses are similarly evaluated by integrating the infinitesimal losses along the height of the device, by considering the external temperature in the outer fiberglass layer and the ambient temperature. Since the device is placed in an indoor laboratory, the heat exchange with the ambient air is considered as $1 \text{ W/m}^2 \text{ K}$.

$$\Phi_{\text{conv}} = \frac{1}{H_{\text{sample}} - H_{\text{th}}} \int_{H_{\text{th}}}^{H_{\text{sample}}} h_{\text{air}} (T_{\text{fgext}} - T_{\text{air}}) dh \quad \text{eq. 5}$$

where:

- h_{air} is the heat transfer coefficient with ambient, assumed to be $1 \text{ W/m}^2 \text{ K}$;
- T_{fgext} is the temperature of the outer surface of fiberglass layer;
- T_{air} is the temperature of the air (ambient).

2.4.2 Experimental Results

A set of concrete samples were provided by Arraela. They are listed in the following table.

Table 5: Concrete samples list. Tested samples are marked with . ⌚ indicates that the sample is under test

Sample name	Concrete name
MA95-M1 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HEATEK-AC
MA98-M4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HEATEK-AC ***
ET 66-M1 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HEATEK-RV
CE 17-M2 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HEATEK-RC
CE17-M8 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HEATEK-RC ***
CE 13-M1 ⌚	HEATEK-RC*
ET64-M1 ⌚	HEATEK-RV **
MA98-M3 ⌚	HEATEK-AC **
CE23-M1 ⌚	HEATEK-RC **

* 5 days in oil at 150 °C
 ** 40 cycles in air ($T_{\text{amb}} - 333^\circ\text{C}$)
 *** 40 cycles in oil ($T_{\text{amb}} - 333^\circ\text{C}$)

For each sample, 3 set of tests are done, each one from 100 to 400 in 50 °C steps in order to assure a good quality and repeatability of results. For samples that have been submitted to oil contact, only results below 350°C make sense, since the oil starts degrading above such a temperature.

A summary of the calculated thermal conductivities can be found in Table 6:

Table 6: Thermal conductivity results in W/m K

Mat.\T (°C)	100	150	200	250	300	350	400
HEATEK- RV	0.98 ± 0.04	1.02 ± 0.03	1.08 ± 0.02	1.15 ± 0.02	1.23 ± 0.02	1.33 ± 0.02	1.45 ± 0.02
HEATEK-RC	0.64 ± 0.03	0.74 ± 0.02	0.82 ± 0.02	0.89 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.02	1.00 ± 0.02
HEATEK-RC (cycled in oil)	1.02 ± 0.05	1.05 ± 0.03	1.09 ± 0.02	1.13 ± 0.02	1.18 ± 0.02	1.23 ± 0.02	--
HEATEK-AC	1.13 ± 0.04	1.23 ± 0.04	1.33 ± 0.04	1.42 ± 0.02	1.51 ± 0.02	1.59 ± 0.02	1.67 ± 0.02
HEATEK-AC (cycled in oil)	1.23 ± 0.03	1.41 ± 0.03	1.54 ± 0.03	1.62 ± 0.02	1.65 ± 0.02	1.63 ± 0.02	-

The thermal conductivity of samples that have been submitted to thermal cycling increases.

ET 66-M1 (HEATEK-RV)

After measuring its thermal conductivity once, a colour change is observed (Figure 11). This change of colour is observed in all the samples that have not been previously cycled immersed in oil.

Figure 11: HEATEK-RV sample (ET 66-M1) previous (left) and after (right) measuring thermal conductivity.

The mean values can be calculated using the following regression curve (see eq. 6), and are listed in Table 7:

$$\lambda = 3 * 10^{-6}T^2 + 5 * 10^{-5}T + 0,9453$$

$$r^2 = 0.8305$$

eq. 6

Table 7 shows the thermal conductivity results of the three measurement campaigns performed.

Table 7: Thermal conductivity data for HEATEK- RV

1 st measurement		2 nd measurement		3 rd measurement	
Electric heater set point/ Temperature at the upper surface of the sample [°C]	$\lambda [W(m^{\circ}C)^{-1}]$	Electric heater set point/ Temperature at the upper surface of the sample [°C]	$\lambda [W(m^{\circ}C)^{-1}]$	Electric heater set point/ Temperature at the upper surface of the sample [°C]	$\lambda [W(m^{\circ}C)^{-1}]$
100 / 75	1.02 ± 0.04	100 / 75	0.84 ± 0.03	100 / 75	0.84 ± 0.03
150 / 81	1.06 ± 0.04	150 / 109	1.04 ± 0.03	150 / 110	0.96 ± 0.03
200 / 117	0.94 ± 0.03	200 / 146	1.06 ± 0.02	200 / 149	0.94 ± 0.02
250 / 152	1.00 ± 0.02	250 / 189	1.08 ± 0.02	250 / 187	1.13 ± 0.02
300 / 190	1.09 ± 0.02	300 / 227	1.12 ± 0.02	300 / 228	1.11 ± 0.02
350 / 225	1.12 ± 0.02	350 / 272	1.18 ± 0.02	350 / 271	1.22 ± 0.02
400 / 273	1.15 ± 0.02	400 / 301	1.26 ± 0.02	400 / 319	1.24 ± 0.02
450 / 318	1.28 ± 0.02	450 / 318	1.28 ± 0.02	450 / 362	1.38 ± 0.02

The following graphic (see Figure 12) shows the thermal conductivity results for this sample.

Figure 12: Effective thermal conductivity of HEATEK- RV**CE 18-M8 (HEATEK-RC)**

Table 8 shows the measured results for HEATEK-RC. In this case, only the first series was performed at intervals of 50 °C; the other two series were performed at intervals of 100 °C in order to comply with the project deadlines.

Table 8: Thermal conductivity data for HEATEK- RC

1 st measurement		2 nd measurement		3 rd measurement	
Electric heater set point/ Temperature at the upper surface of the sample [°C]	$\lambda [W(m^{\circ}C)^{-1}]$	Electric heater set point/ Temperature at the upper surface of the sample [°C]	$\lambda [W(m^{\circ}C)^{-1}]$	Electric heater set point/ Temperature at the upper surface of the sample [°C]	$\lambda [W(m^{\circ}C)^{-1}]$
100 / 73	0.53 ± 0.04	100 / 73	0.63 ± 0.03		
150 / 103	0.67 ± 0.02	150 / 139	0.71 ± 0.02	150 / 118	0.64 ± 0.02
200 / 139	0.78 ± 0.02				
250 / 180	0.82 ± 0.02	250 / 196	0.82 ± 0.02	250 / 203	0.74 ± 0.01
300 / 225	0.90 ± 0.02				
350 / 275	0.97 ± 0.02	350 / 286	1.02 ± 0.02	350 / 290	0.95 ± 0.02
400 / 328	1.01 ± 0.02				
450 / 397	1.05 ± 0.02	450 / 397	1.05 ± 0.02	450 / 397	1.05 ± 0.02

The mean values can be calculated using the following regression curve (see eq. 7), and are listed in Table 8:

$$\lambda = -3 * 10^{-6}T^2 + 0,0027T + 0,4034$$

$$r^2 = 0.9471$$

eq. 7

The following graphic (Figure 13) shows the thermal conductivity results for this sample.

Figure 13: Effective thermal conductivity of HEATEK-RC

In Figure 13 the values placed below the regression line correspond with the 3rd measurement. This, together with the change in colour, leads us to think that there may be a variation in the composition of the concrete. This will be verified when comparing these results with those obtained from sample CE23-M1 (40 cycles in air).

CE18-M8 sample (HEATEK-RC. 40 cycles in oil ($T_{amb} - 333\text{ °C}$))

The same procedure as for the previous samples was followed. It has been checked that the oil evaporates and degrades above 340°C. Table 9 shows the measured results for HEATEK-RC (40 cycles in oil).

Figure 14: Thermocouples inlet where the oil condensation can be observed.

<i>1st measurement</i>	
Electric heater set point/ Temperature at the upper surface of the sample [°C]	$\lambda [W(m^{\circ}C)^{-1}]$
100 / 66	1.04 ± 0.05
150 / 123	0.94 ± 0.03
250 / 235	1.13 ± 0.02
350 / 320	1.12 ± 0.02

Table 9. Thermal conductivity data for HEATEK-RC (cycled in oil)

The mean values can be calculated using the following regression curve (see eq. 8), and are listed in Table 9:

$$\lambda = 10^{-6}T^2 + 4 * 10^{-4}T + 0,9713$$

$$r^2 = 0.7921$$

eq. 8

2.5 OIL ANALYSIS

An indirect way of checking if concrete samples were degraded somehow is by the analysis of the thermal oil in contact with them. Moreover, if there is any oil degradation during the tests, it can be detected as well. Oil samples were sent to Tekniker, and the results of the analyses are shown in Table 10. In addition, an oil sample extracted from Microsol – facility at CNRS has been characterized. This last oil sample has suffered 900 working hours, so its analysis is a good indicator when comparing the other oil samples.

For the oil samples that have been in contact with HEATEK-AC and HEATEK-RV, the flash and fire points could not be quantified since the samples were contaminated with water during the long term cycling test described in section 2.1. After testing the first concrete grade (HEATEK-RC), a leakage of cooling water loop into the oil occurred.

The results of the analysis show no major differences among all the oil samples. The main differences are related to the viscosity index, the particle index and the water content. The oil samples without water contamination have a viscosity at 40°C close to the value of the ‘as received’ oil (16.1 mm²/s). The viscosity values of all samples are in the same range. The main consequence of having water in two oil samples is that both flash point and fire point cannot be determined, because water bubbles appear at around 100°C and the analysis technique cannot be applied. It is also worth mentioning that water can promote oil degradation. On the other hand, since very low amounts (<5 ppm) of inorganic elements like P, Zn, Na, Si and Fe are observed in the oil, it is confirmed that concrete components have not been transferred into the oil upon the cycling. Particle index (dimensionless) is an indication of solids in the oil. Solids can promote the degradation of the oil and affect the performance and safety of the oil loop components and equipment. From the results displayed in Table 10 and after discussing them with the responsible expert of the analysis, it can be said that a particle index of 15 (HEATEK-AC and HEATEK-RV) is pretty high. Therefore, it is worthy to pay attention to potential existence of solids and the potential degradation of concrete samples they may mean.

Table 10: Results of Jarythem DBT oil analysis after about 42 days cycling tests in contact with different HEATEK concrete samples, from Microsol installation at CNRS and as received

Property of thermal oil (Jarythem DBT)	Units	oil in contact with HEATEK-AC 1064 h @ 50°C-325°C under N ₂	oil in contact with HEATEK-RC 993 h @ 50°C-325°C under N ₂	oil in contact with HEATEK-RV 999 h @ 50°C-340°C under N ₂	oil from Microsol (CNRS) 900 h @ 120°C-300°C under N ₂	As received oil
Viscosity @40°C	mm ² /s	17.2	17.0	17.1	17.0	16.1
Viscosity @100°C	mm ² /s	3.3	3.2	3.2	3.2	3.12
IV		25	9	27	7	12
Density @20°C	g/ml	1.0448	1.0438	1.0442	1.0445	1.0438
Flash point	°C	N.A.	204	N.A.	204	212
Pour point	°C	-32	-33	-32	-32	-30
Fire point	°C	N.A.	258	N.A.	262	258
Thermal conductivity @24°C	W/mK	0.130	0.130	0.128	0.128	0.1276
Particle index in the oil	-	15	4	13	2	0
Water	%	0.28	0.07	0.34	<0.1	0

3. MATERIALS SELECTION ACCORDING TO APPLICATION

Table 11 resumes the thermophysical characteristics to consider when assigning material to each specific application. Although the 'Cost factor' line is a rough relative approach, this parameter yields to disregard HEATEK-AC which is expected to be 10 times more expensive than the other grades of concrete.

Table 11: Main concrete characteristics to influence the thermal design of the storage tank

	HEATEK-AC	HEATEK-RC	HEATEK-RV
Main characteristics	Granular material: Natural (magnetite, including FeO content)	Granular material: non-metallic urban wastes	Granular material: metallic wastes from blast furnaces
ρ (kg/m ³)	3925	2040	3105
C_p (kJ/kg.K)		1.7-2.6	0.75-1.25
Volumetric capacity, ρC_p , (KJ/m ³ .K)		~4386	~3027
λ (W/m K)		0.6-1.0	1-1.2
Cost factor	10/1	1/1	1/1

The driving parameter used to assign material to each application is the thermal conductivity. Therefore, it was decided to use:

- **HEATEK-RC for insulating slab**
- **HEATEK-RV for tank walls and filler**, in spite of its lower volumetric heat capacity compared to HEATEK-RC.

The tank walls and the foundations are reinforced with steel bars (see section 5).

4. BASIC SIZING OF STORAGE TANK WITH FILLER

The storage tank has an effective storage capacity of 2MWh, according to Polyphem proposal. Since it is a thermocline system, there will be some volume of the tank occupied by the thermocline region that will not be useful (see Figure 15). In order to estimate the size of this volume in the Polyphem plant, CIEMAT's basic model¹ has been used, assuming a design oil flowrate of 0.7 kg/s. According to this simulation, around 25% of the tank volume may be occupied by the thermocline region. Therefore, considering a conservative risk margin of 30%, the size of a tank with a **storage capacity of 2.6 MWh** seems appropriate. In addition, it is being considered in the operation modes that part of the energy available at moderate temperature in the thermocline region may be used for preheating and also feeding the ORC engine to generate electricity. So 2.6 MWh is a conservative value.

Figure 15: Simulated temperature profile evolution from a full charged tank

Considering the C_p of the HEATEK-RV to be used as filler material (see Table 11) and of the Jarytherm DBT oil (Table 1) and the 2.6 MWh storage capacity, the oil volume and tank diameter are plotted versus porosity in Figure 16. Since the volumetric heat capacities of the oil ($\sim 1951 \text{ kJ/m}^3\text{K}$, Table 1) and the filler ($\sim 3027 \text{ kJ/m}^3\text{K}$, Table 11) are different, the required tank volume does not vary as a linear function of porosity: 15.7 m^3 for 0.4 porosity, 15.0 m^3 for 0.3 porosity and 14.5 m^3 for 0.2 porosity.

A free volume over the thermal oil must be considered for the N_2 atmosphere in the tank. The design height of this free volume is set at 0.2 m.

Finally, assuming a porosity of 0.4, the effective storage volume is 15.7 m^3 . For a cylindrical shape of tank 2.6 m in diameter, the effective storage height is 3 m. The total height of the tank is 3.2 m, the inner volume of the tank is around 17 m^3 . The volume of oil is 6.3 m^3 and the mass of filler is 29200 kg.

¹ An optimized simulation model for a thermocline tank will be developed along the Polyphem project.

Figure 16: Sizes of a cylindrical tank with 2.6 MWh storage capacity using Jarytherm DBT oil and HEATEK-RV as filler with different porosities. Blue line is the required oil volume using the secondary y-axis scale.

5. TANK AND FOUNDATIONS DESIGNS

The thermocline tank to be designed in present document, is cylinder shaped **1.30 m in radius and 3.20 m in height** (inner dimensions) supported by an insulating slab. The thickness of the walls will be studied and finally set to 0.50 m and the rest of structural elements will be set to 0.40 m in thickness.

Both the roof and the walls are covered with refractory insulating plates. This thermal insulation can be modified under demand by changing the conductivity of the material or the thickness.

5.1 THERMAL AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

5.1.1 Materials

Tank is made with various grades of thermal concrete HEATEK[®], **reinforced with steel bars**. Follow are listed the main characteristics of the different materials to be used in the calculations for the computational model:

- **HEATEK-RV**: according to its resistance properties at high temperatures and the demonstrated compatibility with the thermal oil, has been the one chosen for the structure of the tank. Main parameters are following:

Density → 3.0 t/m³

Young modulus → 40.50 GPa (@25°C) and 14.50 GPa (@700°C)

Poisson coefficient → 0.20

Thermal conductivity → Figure 12

Thermal expansion coefficient → $13 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$

- **HEATEK-RC**: its resistance properties do not improve in comparison to RV, however the thermal conductivity is lower, so this is the one chosen for the insulating slab. These are the values considered:

Density → 1.85 t/m³

Young modulus → 18.00 GPa (@25°C) and 10.50 GPa (@500°C)

Poisson coefficient → 0.20

Thermal conductivity → Figure 13

Thermal expansion coefficient → $12 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$

- Reinforcement steel U-3CR12:
 - Density → 7.68 t/m^3
 - Young modulus → 231 GPa (@100°C) and 150 GPa (@500°C)
 - Thermal conductivity → 30.0 W/m K (@100°C) and 40.0 W/m K (@500°C)
 - Thermal expansion coefficient → (0 to 500°C) $12.3 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$
- Outer thermal insulation: using refractory insulating plates 20 cm thickness and following properties:
 - Density → 0.24 t/m^3
 - Thermal conductivity → 0.026 W/m K
- Natural ground: granitic rock, as is common in the rock mass in Pyrenees. These are the average values considered:
 - Density → 2.6 t/m^3
 - Young modulus → 30 GPa
 - Poisson coefficient → 0.20
 - Thermal conductivity → 2.80 W/m K
 - Thermal expansion coefficient → $8 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$

5.1.2 Size of the model

In finite elements models, the size of the component and the size of its close environment are key parameters since they govern the accuracy achieved during the calculation process and the computational time necessary to get it done.

The component studied here is the storage tank. The size of its close environment –named as the guard, in both horizontal and vertical directions- is expressed in percentage of the tank diameter. We have developed a sensitivity analysis to the size of the guard, comparing the values of transmittance (energy losses per unit area) of the model. The Figure 17 shows the evolution of the transmittance in the foundation, as a function of the guard:

Figure 17: Transmittance to the environment surrounding the tank as a function of the guard in the model

As depicted in Figure 17, the transmittance increases with increasing guard. When the guard equals the tank diameter, the transmittance does not vary any more (horizontal asymptote).

A tank of much higher capacity ($\varnothing 50$ m) has been modelled. The results of transmittance to the ground are plotted in Figure 18. The transmittance to the ground decreases with increasing guard. A similar conclusion is observed: from a ratio guard/diameter >1 (guard > 50 m), the transmittance to the ground comes to zero and remains unchanged.

Figure 18: Transmittance to the ground as a function of the guard in the model

In summary, we will adopt a guard of one (1) diameter around the tank in order to obtain an accurate result.

5.1.3 Software

For main thermal, structural and deformational models we have worked with Ansys Mechanical Pro[®]. This software is considered the world leader for FEM calculations.

5.1.4 Additional boundary conditions

The tank will be installed at Themis solar platform in Targassonne (France). Climate here is wet Mediterranean and high mountain Oceanic, with minimum temperatures around -11 °C in winter and maximum 24 °C in summer. A sensitivity analysis of the FEM to these temperatures is reported in the following section 5.1.5.

Likewise, the terrain temperature will be taken into account, considering the following profile of geothermic temperatures represented in Figure 19:

Figure 19: Profile of underground temperature considered in the model

5.1.5 Thermal study FEM

From the geometry described above, materials properties and boundary conditions, we have developed a complete analysis of the thermal behaviour of the tank (also taking into account the thermal and stiffness effect of the steel reinforcement inside). In the next pages are shown the processes carried out and the main results obtained.

5.1.5.1 Sensitivity analysis

The aim of this section is to analyse the influence of the ambient temperature on the thermal behaviour of the tank, taking into account the insulating effect of the outer plates.

From a single 3D FEM of the tank, with same outer thermal insulation and internal working temperature, we have studied the influence of the ambient temperature on the results. In Figure 20 and Figure 21 are shown a comparison between isothermal curves and the transmittances with outside ambient temperature of -11°C and +24°C respectively:

Figure 20: Isothermal curves and transmittance obtained for min/max outside ambient temperature of -11°C (left) and +24°C (right).

Below are plotted two 2D curves with the comparative evolution of the temperature at the external face for both ambient temperatures -11°C and +24°C:

Figure 21: Temperature at the external face as a function of height

As can be seen, the deviations between both situations are minor. For the simulation reported in the following pages, the ambient temperature will be indicated in every cases.

5.1.5.2 FEM model definition

Geometry

Mesh

- Number of nodes: $0.25 \cdot 10^6$
- Number of elements: $0.16 \cdot 10^6$

Figure 22: Geometry and mesh considered in the model

The mesh model presented in Figure 22 is densified in critical regions. It is built using well-formed elements, as shown by the orthogonal quality: Minimum: 0.22 - Maximum: 0.99 - Average: 0.83. Numerical errors and uncertainties are therefore minimized. The distribution of the size of the elements is presented in Figure 23.

Figure 23: Distribution of the size of the elements of the thermal model

5.1.5.3 Boundary conditions

Two different scenarios are considered, as shown in Figure 24:

Figure 24: Scenarios considered for the temperature distribution in the model

In both cases, the boundary conditions for the convection heat transfer to the atmosphere are: outside temperature +15 °C; convection heat transfer coefficient 15 W/m² K

5.1.5.4 Geometric sensitivity analysis

This analysis is done in the walls of the tank, by varying the thickness of the wall and the thickness of the insulating material. The aim is to decrease the difference of temperature between the outer and the inner face of the wall at the thermocline region. The reduction of this difference of temperature implies lower steel reinforcement. For this, two control points have been located in the model in the most critical section (see green colour points in Figure 25):

Figure 25: Area of interest for the sensitivity of the model to the geometry

Figure 26 shows the graphics with the results obtained:

Figure 26: Temperature difference in the area of interest as a function of the thickness of the insulation

The main conclusion is that the temperature difference is more sensible to the change of wall thickness than to the outer insulating system: 5 cm less of wall thickness results in a reduction of the difference of 7 °C (10%). According to this, we propose the following thicknesses for the structural elements:

- Walls → 0.50 m
- Roof → 0.40 m
- Bottom slab → 0.40 m
- Insulating slab → 0.40 m
- Insulating plates → 0.20 m

Remark 1: The roof is made of a 0.40 m flat slab, due to the low diameter of this tank. For up-scaled tank of higher thermal storage capacity ($\phi > 10$ m) the solution could be a compound hat-shaped roof, made of a central steel domo supported by pillars inside the tank and surrounded by a flat concrete slab as illustrated in Figure 27:

Figure 27: Design of the roof for up-scaled thermal storage tank ($\phi > 10$ m)

Remark 2: Due to the good geotechnical and thermal properties expected for the granitic ground, we choose a 0.40 m slab made of HEATEK-RC for the insulating bottom slab (below the tank). Several cylinder shape holes will be made in this bottom slab, in order to lower the thermal conductivity of the whole element. The hollow volume, occupied by air, represents about 30% of the total volume of the slab in the model designed.

5.1.5.5 Temperature distribution (equilibrium situation)

The distribution of temperature in the tank structure and in the surrounding is presented in Figure 28 for both scenarios. In both cases the temperature of the supporting ground remains low (114°C in scenario n°2), thanks to the insulating effect of the HEATEK-RC bottom slab. Therefore the geometrical predesign of the insulating system is valid.

Maximum temperature in the natural ground: 38°C

Maximum temperature in the natural ground: 114°C

Figure 28: Temperature distribution in the walls and in the ground for the two scenarios considered -outside ambient temperature of -11°C (left) and +24°C (right).

5.1.6 Structural analysis (no thermal)

5.1.6.1 Loads

- Own weight:
 - Concrete densities: 30 KN/m³ (HEATEK-RV) and 15 KN/m³ (HEATEK-RC)
 - Steel density: 78.50 KN/m³
 - Filler density: 19 KN/m³ (internal friction 35°)
 - Thermal oil density → 9.68 KN/m³ @100°C; 8.96 KN/m³ @200°C; 8.18 KN/m³ @300°C
- Filler horizontal thrust → Rest coefficient K0 (saturated of oil). According to Coulomb theory $E = \gamma \times h \times K0$
- Additional inner pressure (N₂ atmosphere) → 150 mbar (15 KN/m²)
- Overload on the roof due to temporary O&M activities → 1.5 KN/m²
- Temperature: we use the most unfavourable scenario from a tensional point of view, which is scenario n° 1 (thermocline zone in the middle). The corresponding temperature distribution is reported in Figure 29:

Figure 29: Temperature distribution in the walls, input for the stress-strain analysis

5.1.6.2 Ground ballast

To calculate the ballast module we use the Vesic formula. The value obtained is $10.6 \cdot 10^6$ kN/m³:

Ballast modulus (Vesic formulation)	
Es. Young Modulus (MN/m ²)	30 000
B. Foundation width (m)	3.10
Poisson's ratio	0.30
ks (KN/m ³)	10 634 527

5.1.6.3 Filler horizontal thrust

Coulomb formulation has been used for obtaining the static thrust. The scheme is shown in Figure 30:

Figure 30: Scheme of the horizontal loads due to the filler

The filler is saturated in oil, resulting in an immersed density of 1.32 t/m³:

Oil density (t/m ³)	Dry density (t/m ³)	Porosity η (%)	Saturated density (t/m ³)	Submerged density (t/m ³)
0.96	3.11	40.00	3.49	2.53

In this situation, the filler horizontal thrust is derived as follows:

INPUTS	
H. Ground depth (m)	3.20
γ. Backfill density (t/m ³)	3.105
γ sum. Backfill submerged density (t/m ³)	2.53
γ w. Water density (t/m ³)	0.96
γ sat. Backfill saturated density (t/m ³)	3.49
Hw. Water table height (m)	3.20
Angles	
φ. Soil internal friction angle	42.00
δ. Structure-soil friction angle	0.00

5.1.6.4 Mechanical properties

These are the main parameters considered:

- HEATEK-RV tensile strength (330 °C) → 5.0 MPa
- HEATEK-RV compression strength (330 °C) → 50 MPa
- Steel yield strength (330 °C) → 400 MPa

5.1.6.5 Stress-deformation analysis related with the thermal gradient (Scenario nº 1)

Figure 31: Geometry and mesh of the model of tank for the stress-strain analysis

Results of **Deformations** (equilibrium situation)

Figure 32: Horizontal (left) and vertical (right) deformations of the tank given by the simulation

Figure 33: Total deformation of the tank in 3D (left) and 2D (right) given by the simulation

Results of **Stresses** (equilibrium situation)

Roof and bottom slabs: the concrete is able to support the compression stress and traction stress related with the temperature difference, so we design a minimum steel reinforcement #12/200 in each roof and bottom slab (see Figure 34). With that, the stress in both roof and bottom is far below the yield stress of the slabs.

X axis (horizontal)

FOUNDATION	
Depth (m)	0.30
Maximum compression ANSYS (MPa)	-8.40
Maximum tension ANSYS (MPa)	2.50
Coefficients of loads	1.00
Design maximum compression (MPa)	-8.40
Design maximum tension (MPa)	2.50
Concrete characteristic tensile strength (MPa)	5.00
Concrete strength factor of safety	1.00
Design concrete tensile strength (MPa)	5.00
Neutral axis position (m)	0.069
Total tension / m.l. (t)	8.60
Tension supported by concrete (t)	34.40
Tension supported by steel (t)	-25.80
Steel Yield stress (MPa)	400.00
Steel strength factor of safety	1.00
Design steel tensile strength (MPa)	400.00
Required steel area (cm2/m)	0.00
Layers	1

ROOF	
Depth (m)	0.30
Maximum compression ANSYS (MPa)	-4.54
Maximum tension ANSYS (MPa)	4.60
Coefficients of loads	1.00
Design maximum compression (MPa)	-4.54
Design maximum tension (MPa)	4.60
Concrete characteristic tensile strength (MPa)	5.00
Concrete strength factor of safety	1.00
Design concrete tensile strength (MPa)	5.00
Neutral axis position (m)	0.151
Total tension / m.l. (t)	34.73
Tension supported by concrete (t)	75.49
Tension supported by steel (t)	-40.77
Steel Yield stress (MPa)	400.00
Steel strength factor of safety	1.00
Design steel tensile strength (MPa)	400.00
Required steel area (cm2/m)	0
Layers	1

Figure 34: Stress profile in roof and bottom slabs (horizontal direction)

Horizontal steel reinforcement in the wall: due to the temperature difference, a steel ratio of 63.50 cm²/m is necessary, which means two layers of 25/150 (see Figure 35).

Z axis (horizontal)

WALL HORIZONTAL	
Depth (m)	0.40
Maximum compression ANSYS (MPa)	2.90
Maximum tension ANSYS (MPa)	19.80
Coefficients of loads	1.00
Design maximum compression (MPa)	2.90
Design maximum tension (MPa)	19.80
Concrete characteristic tensile strength (MPa)	5.00
Concrete strength factor of safety	1.00
Design concrete tensile strength (MPa)	5.00
Neutral axis position (m)	0.400
Total tension / m.l. (t)	454.00
Tension supported by concrete (t)	200.00
Tension supported by steel (t)	254.00
Steel Yield stress (MPa)	400.00
Steel strength factor of safety	1.00
Design steel tensile strength (MPa)	400.00
Required steel area (cm²/m)	63.50
Layers	2
	31.75

Figure 35: Stress profile in the wall (horizontal direction)

Vertical steel reinforcement in the wall: due to the temperature difference, a steel reinforcement of 25/200 is necessary in the outer region and a double layer of 16/150 is necessary in the inner region (see Figure 36). With that, the stress in the wall is 8% below the yield stress in the critical region of the thermocline and it is 37% below the yield stress in the top and bottom parts of the wall.

Y axis (vertical)

WALL INNER VERTICAL		WALL OUTER VERTICAL	
Depth (m)	0.40	Depth (m)	0.40
Maximum compression ANSYS (MPa)	-15.15	Maximum compression ANSYS (MPa)	-21.30
Maximum tension ANSYS (MPa)	17.80	Maximum tension ANSYS (MPa)	19.90
Coefficients of loads	1.00	Coefficients of loads	1.00
Design maximum compression (MPa)	-15.15	Design maximum compression (MPa)	-21.30
Design maximum tension (MPa)	17.80	Design maximum tension (MPa)	19.90
Concrete characteristic tensile strength (MPa)	5.00	Concrete characteristic tensile strength (MPa)	5.00
Concrete strength factor of safety	1.00	Concrete strength factor of safety	1.00
Design concrete tensile strength (MPa)	5.00	Design concrete tensile strength (MPa)	5.00
Neutral axis position (m)	0.216	Neutral axis position (m)	0.193
Total tension / m.l. (t)	192.32	Total tension / m.l. (t)	192.24
Tension supported by concrete (t)	108.04	Tension supported by concrete (t)	96.60
Tension supported by steel (t)	84.27	Tension supported by steel (t)	95.64
Steel Yield stress (MPa)	400.00	Steel Yield stress (MPa)	400.00
Steel strength factor of safety	1.00	Steel strength factor of safety	1.00
Design steel tensile strength (MPa)	400.00	Design steel tensile strength (MPa)	400.00
Required steel area (cm²/m)	21.07	Required steel area (cm²/m)	23.91
Layers	2	Layers	1
	10.53		

Figure 36: Stress profile in the wall (vertical direction)

Insulating slab: This slab made of HEATEK-RC concrete grade will be under the tank with a 0.40 m thickness an oversized radius of 0.30 m. Both structural elements (tank and insulating slab) will not be joined, there will be only a frictional contact between both concrete faces (HEATEK-RV and HEATEK-RC). The main results are presented in Figure 37, Figure 38 and Figure 39:

Deformations (equilibrium situation)

X axis (horizontal)

Y axis (vertical)

Figure 37: Deformation of the insulating slab in horizontal (left) and vertical (right) directions

Figure 38: Total deformation of the insulating slab

Stresses (equilibrium situation)

X axis (horizontal)

Z axis (horizontal)

Y axis (vertical)

Figure 39: Stress distribution in the insulating slab along the 3 axes

In all the cases, the concrete is able to resist to the compression stresses and strains generated by the thermal gradient, so we decide to place a minimum steel reinforcement #12/200 in both upper and bottom regions of the slab, placing these bars in the nerves between the holes.

5.1.6.6 Stress-deformation study without thermal environment

A 3D model is used in this approach. This model includes all the loads described in the above sections, except the thermal ones.

The thrust over the walls (in kN/m²) is shown in Figure 40:

Figure 40: 3D mesh (a) and thrust on the wall (b) in the 3D simulation approach

As can be seen in Figure 41, the maximum bending moment is only 12.80 kN.m/m, which means that the non-thermal loads are very small. The structural calculation is dominated by the thermal load. This observation validates the steel reinforcement proposed in the above sections.

Deformations (mm) in X axis (horizontal)

Bending moment (ELU). M11 (KN m/m)

Bending moment (ELU). M22 (KN m/m)

Figure 41: Deformation and bending moments on the wall in the 3D simulation approach

5.1.6.7 Roof and walls connection

The tank has an inner pressure of 150 mbar (1.50 ton/m²) so we will make a last check for the necessary bars that connect the roof to the walls. As can be seen below, the number and diameter of the bars needed is lower than the vertical reinforcement inside the walls (as calculated before):

Anchor stress checking	
Axial tension (kg)	3 169
Shear (kg)	0
Partial factor of safety	1.50
Factored axial tension (kg)	4 754
Factored shear (kg)	0
Number of Anchors	40.00
Design axial tension (kg)	118.84
Design shear (kg)	0.00
Anchor diameter (mm)	12.00
Yield stress (MPa)	400.00
Steel strength factor of safety	1.15
Design Yield stress (MPa)	347.83
Design shear stress (Mpa)	200.82
Axial stress checking	
Tension (Mpa)	10.51
Valid	Yes
factor of safety	33.10
Shear stress checking	
Tension (Mpa)	0.00
Valid	Yes
factor of safety	-
Von Mises tension	
Valid	Yes
factor of safety	33.10

5.1.6.8 Steel reinforcements summary

This is the steel reinforcement proposed for the tank:

TERMOCLINE TANK			
Element	Reinforcement		
	cm2/m	Type	Layers
Foundation. Both faces h = 0.40 m	Minimum ratio	12/200 (5.65)	1
Wall. External face. Vertical reinforcement h = 0.50 m	23.91	25/200 (24.54)	1
Wall. Internal face. Vertical reinforcement h = 0.50 m	10.53	16/150 (13.40)	2
Wall. External face. Horizontal reinforcement h = 0.50 m	Minimum ratio	12/200 (5.65)	1
Wall. Internal face. Horizontal reinforcement h = 0.50 m	31.75	25/150 (32.72)	2
Roof. Both faces h = 0.40 m	Minimum ratio	12/200 (5.65)	1

5.2 CONNECTING TANK WITH POLYPHEM LOOP: INLET AND OUTLET PIPES

According to the geometry designed in the above section, in this part we will study the behaviour of the thermal oil inside the tank. Our objective is to confirm that the thermocline is not affected by the low value of oil flowrate (0.70 kg/s).

5.2.1 Computational models considered

Since not sufficiently reliable results were obtained using 2D models, so we decided to work in 3D, taking advantage of the possibility of defining the number of inlet and outlet locations in the mesh. The inlet and outlet flowrate of the oil is 0.70 kg/s. Considering such a low value of flowrate, only 2 inlet and 1 outlet points have been considered in the models.

The values of porosity and permeability of the bed (solid filler particles) are key input parameters in the hydraulic model of the storage tank. The main parameters influencing the porosity of a packed bed are the uniformity in size of the particles and the arrangement of the particles in the bed. The porosity of a rectangular arrangement of spherical particles of the same size is around 0.4. This value is used as a reference value for porosity in the following simulations.

On the other hand, the permeability is also governed by the specific size of the particles. The specific size of a particle is the ratio volume/area. For Polyphem, the shape and size of the filler particles are still under investigation. It is therefore assumed in the simulation that the particles are spherical (specific size = $d/6$) and the diameter d is taken as the diameter of the granular material of HEATEK-RV. This diameter varies between 0.8 and 1 cm.

Figure 42: Permeability of a packed bed as function of its porosity and particle size, according to the Ergun-Kozeny approach

We have compared two different beds, covering the range of expected size of particles and 2 different arrangements, represented by the porosity. The permeability of each bed is derived from the Ergun-Kozeny equation (Figure 42).

- Model nº1
 - Particle diameter in the range of 1 – 1.02 cm
 - Porosity: 0.4
 - Permeability of the bed: $1.2 \cdot 10^{-7} m^2$
- Model nº2
 - Particle diameter: 0.8 cm
 - Porosity: 0.2
 - Permeability of the bed: $5.3 \cdot 10^{-9} m^2$.

Remark: The permeability of the bed is a relevant parameter, because the higher the permeability is, the greater number of preferential routes inside the filler exist. If the oil flows locally at high velocity during the charge/discharge mode, ineffective areas may be created, destroying the thermocline layer.

The properties of the Jarytherm DBT oil considered in the CFD calculations are:

- Density: 0.987 t/m³ @100°C; 0.914 t/m³ @200°C and 0.834 t/m³ @300°C
- Kinematic viscosity: 3.0 mm²/s @100°C; 0.82 mm²/s @200°C and 0.44 mm²/s @300°C

In both cases, the oil inlet is made with 2 tubes at the centre top and the oil outlet is made with one tube at the centre bottom.

We have chosen a variable density mesh, presented in Figure 43, achieving a high density of nodes in the regions where strong changes of the variables and geometries are expected. The distribution of the size of the elements is presented in Figure 44.

- Number of nodes: 0.56 10⁶
- Number of elements: 1.24 10⁶
- Orthogonal quality:
 - Minimum: 0.19
 - Maximum: 0.99
 - Average: 0.85

Figure 43: Mesh of the model for the fluid simulation of the oil flow in the tank

Figure 44: Distribution of the size of the elements of the fluid dynamic model

5.2.2 Results

In general, the lowest the oil flow is, the most stable it is. Fluid velocity in the range 1-2 cm/s has been confirmed by measurements made on a prototype of thermocline tank without filler by a partner of the project Polyphem.

The hydraulic behaviour of the two models described above is shown in Figure 45. No major deviation between both models is observed. The velocity of the oil inside the tank is very slow in most of the volume (<1 mm/s), due to the low oil flowrate in the Polyphem loop (0.7 kg/s).

Figure 45: Fluid velocity in the tank in two cases for the permeability and porosity, (a) model n°1 and (b) model n°2

The model n°1 is the worst case, featuring a value of permeability 20 times higher than in n° 2. Output data obtained for model n° 1 are presented in Figure 46 and Figure 47.

Figure 46 presents the velocity field and the preferential routes for the oil. The main flow is in vertical direction. In this worst case, the oil velocity is around 0.5 mm/s in almost all the tank. Instabilities are observed only in regions close to the inlet and outlet points. A vortex is created at the bottom near the wall. This is due to the brutal change from vertical to horizontal direction of the flow and crossing with the vertical flow in the central region of the tank. In most cases the thermocline region is far from the bottom, therefore it is not affected by this vortex. A stable behaviour of the thermocline layer is expected during the operational modes.

(a) Vertical velocity in a cross-section in m/s

(b) Preferential routes in a cross-section in m/s

(c) Volume rendering in m/s

Figure 46: Fluid velocity in the tank for high permeability (model n°1), cross-section (a) & (b), volume rendering (c)
 POLYPHEM D3.1: Report on the design and specifications of filler, tank and foundations

Figure 47 shows the distribution of velocity of the oil in selected horizontal planes in the upper region of the tank (a) and in the thermocline zone (b). The distribution becomes more uniform when moving from the top to the bottom. For the selected planes, the reduced colour bar clearly shows that the velocity ranges below 1 mm/s. The distribution is uniform in the plane representing the thermocline region, so no variation in the thermocline is expected.

Figure 47: Velocity of oil in the upper region (a) and in the thermocline region (b)

6. SUMMARY AND MAIN OUTCOMES ON DESIGN

A thermocline tank for an effective 2 MWh storage capacity has been designed using Jarytherm DBT thermal oil as heat transfer fluid and concrete HEATEK-RV as filler material. The compatibility between these two materials has been proved. Compatibility means that no major changes either in their thermal and structural properties have been observed after testing the two materials in contact, submitted to a thermal sequence that may be representative enough of its real operation sequence. A specific device has been designed and constructed to carry out such a testing.

The tank will have 1.30 m radius and 3.20 m height (inner dimensions). This size has been calculated taking into account the measured heat capacity of the filler and HTF, assuming a 30% risk margin in storage capacity due to the expected size of thermocline region, and some room for input and output connections.

Tank walls will have 0.50 m and tank roof 0.40 m thickness. Both roof and walls of this tank will be made also with HEATEK-RV reinforced with steel bars according to the following table:

TERMOCLINE TANK			
Element	Reinforcement		
	cm ² /m	Type	Layers
Foundation. Both faces h = 0.40 m	Minimum ratio	12/200 (5.65)	1
Wall. External face. Vertical reinforcement h = 0.50 m	23.91	25/200 (24.54)	1
Wall. Internal face. Vertical reinforcement h = 0.50 m	10.53	16/150 (13.40)	2
Wall. External face. Horizontal reinforcement h = 0.50 m	Minimum ratio	12/200 (5.65)	1
Wall. Internal face. Horizontal reinforcement h = 0.50 m	31.75	25/150 (32.72)	2
Roof. Both faces h = 0.40 m	Minimum ratio	12/200 (5.65)	1

The tank will be supported by an insulating layer of 0.4 m thickness of reinforced HEATEK-RC (see table above). The shape of such insulating layer is the following:

An additional aerial thermal insulation using refractory insulating plates 20 cm in thickness will be used. Structural and thermal calculations have been performed considering granitic rocks for the supporting natural ground.

A thermofluid analysis has been performed to assess the influence of the number and size of inlet and outlet connections. The velocity of the oil in the loop is slow, and it is extremely slow inside the tank. In all conditions, including central position and low number of inlet and outlet oil connection points, the thickness of the thermocline region is expected to remain very stable.

7. ANNEXES

ANNEX 1: JARYTHERM DBT_technical datasheet.pdf

JARYTHERM® DBT

Heat transfer fluid

Synthetic heat transfer fluid, made from a blend of dibenzyltoluene isomers.

APPLICATIONS

Heat transfer installations
by fluid circulation

- Operating from 0°C to + 350 °C in the bulk (370 °C in the film) without air contact. JARYTHERM® DBT is mainly used in the chemical and plastics transformation industries (barrel extruders).

SPECIFICATIONS

- ISO 6743/12 class L-QD-350

JARYTHERM® DBT successfully passes the following Thermal Stability tests (1000h, 350°C):

- ASTM D6743
- DIN 51528
- GB/T 23800-2009

ADVANTAGES

Extended drain interval

Working safety

- Excellent stability to thermal cracking**
Can be used for a long period without the formation of carbon deposits which can foul the circuit. Preserves the heat exchange characteristics of the installation.
- Resistance to oxidation**
A thermal fluid must show good resistance to oxidation, even with limited exposure to oxygen in the air. JARYTHERM® DBT offers this characteristics.

TYPICAL PROPERTIES	METHODS	UNITS	JARYTHERM® DBT			
			20 °C	100 °C	200 °C	300 °C
Density	ISO 3675	kg/m ³	1043	987	914	834
Kinematic viscosity	ISO 3104	mm ² /s	50	3	0.82	0.44
Specific heat capacity	-	kJ/kg °C	1.60	1.81	2.10	2.51
Thermal conductivity	-	W/m °C	0.128	0.121	0.113	0.105

Above characteristics are mean values given as an information.

TYPICAL CHARACTERISTICS	METHODS	UNITS	JARYTHERM® DBT
Flash point (OC)	ISO 2592	°C	200
Fire point	ISO 2592	°C	230
Pour point	ISO 3016	°C	-34
Boiling point (under 760 mm of mercury)	-	°C	390
Total Decomposition Rate – 1000h, 350°C.	GB23800-2009	%	6.9
Operating range	-		
- in the bulk		°C	0 / + 350
- in the film		°C	370

Above characteristics are mean values given as an information.

A few useful conversion factors:

1 kcal/kg. °C = 4184 J/kg. °C

1 kcal/m.h. °C = 1.162 W/m. °C

1 mm Hg = 133 Pa

JARYTHERM® DBT is registered trademark of ARKEMA.

Jarytherm® DBT

Thermodynamic Data

T (°C)	Specific Heat (kJ/kg.°C)	Thermal Conductivity (W/m.°C)	Density (kg/m ³)	Vapour pressure (bar)	Dynamic Viscosity (mPa.s)	Kinematic Viscosity (mm ² /s)
0	1,520	0,130	1059	0,00	274,1	258,8
20	1,580	0,128	1044	0,00	52,3	50,1
40	1,650	0,126	1029	0,00	17,45	17,0
60	1,710	0,125	1014	0,00	7,98	7,87
80	1,780	0,123	1000	0,00	4,43	4,43
100	1,840	0,121	985	0,00	2,80	2,84
120	1,900	0,120	970	0,00	1,94	2,00
140	1,970	0,118	955	0,00	1,43	1,50
160	2,030	0,116	940	0,00	1,11	1,18
180	2,090	0,115	925	0,00	0,89	0,96
200	2,160	0,113	911	0,01	0,74	0,81
220	2,220	0,112	896	0,01	0,62	0,69
240	2,290	0,110	881	0,03	0,54	0,61
260	2,350	0,108	866	0,05	0,47	0,54
280	2,410	0,107	851	0,10	0,42	0,49
300	2,480	0,105	836	0,17	0,37	0,44
320	2,540	0,103	821	0,29	0,34	0,41
340	2,600	0,102	807	0,46	0,31	0,38
360	2,670	0,100	792	0,71	0,28	0,35
380	2,730	0,098	777	1,05	0,26	0,33

ANNEX 2

HEATEK-AC

BEFORE testing (extracted from *H Ac AIRE (MA99 BLOQUE).pdf*)

Element Name	Min	PPM	Max	+/- [*3]
MgO	0	20612	0	16061
Al2O3	0	59190	0	3206
SiO2	0	72836	0	1832
P2O5	0	854	0	270
S	0	15943	0	389
Cl	0	0	0	185
K2O	0	7854	0	156
CaO	0	42614	0	290
Ti	0	8434	0	119
V	0	1078	0	52
Cr	0	0	0	72
Mn	0	1332	0	114
Fe	0	454294	0	1438
Co	0	2276	0	349
Ni	0	1379	0	234
Cu	0	102	0	51
Zn	0	91	0	34
As	0	0	0	12
Se	0	0	0	22
Rb	0	252	0	30
Sr	0	0	0	24
Y	0	1	0	28
Zr	0	72	0	19
Nb	0	0	0	31
Mo	0	0	0	26
Rh	0	0	0	5
Pd	0	0	0	16
Ag	0	0	0	0
Cd	0	0	0	72
Sn	0	0	0	112
Sb	0	0	0	97
Ba	0	0	0	362
La	0	0	0	0
Ce	0	0	0	280
Hf	0	0	0	23
Ta	0	9	0	68
W	0	0	0	46
Pt	0	0	0	13
Au	0	0	0	55
Hg	0	0	0	30
Tl	0	0	0	33
Pb	0	444	0	45
Bi	0	703	0	95
Th	0	0	0	86
U	0	0	0	193

AFTER testing (extracted from *Table hormigones.xlsx*)

Element Name	Min	PPM	Max	+/- [*3]
MgO	0	12713	0	13296
Al2O3	0	27882	0	2395
SiO2	0	43171	0	1486
P2O5	0	3517	0	278
S	0	0	0	183
Cl	0	0	0	127
K2O	0	5156	0	135
CaO	0	92039	0	403
Ti	0	4755	0	102
V	0	1341	0	52
Cr	0	0	0	61
Mn	0	1108	0	108
Fe	0	389164	0	1359
Co	0	0	0	339
Ni	0	763	0	144
Cu	0	82	0	37
Zn	0	76	0	25
As	0	0	0	9
Se	0	0	0	17
Rb	0	122	0	19
Sr	0	0	0	19
Y	0	38	0	22
Zr	0	93	0	16
Nb	0	0	0	29
Mo	0	0	0	20
Rh	0	0	0	6
Pd	0	0	0	17
Ag	0	0	0	0
Cd	0	0	0	53
Sn	0	0	0	129
Sb	0	0	0	100
Ba	0	0	0	311
La	0	0	0	0
Hf	0	0	0	24
Ta	0	9	0	47
W	0	0	0	32
Pt	0	0	0	15
Au	0	0	0	38
Hg	0	0	0	27
Tl	0	0	0	26
Pb	0	279	0	38
Bi	0	331	0	63
Th	0	0	0	67
U	0	0	0	146

HEATEK-RC

BEFORE testing (extracted from *RC AIRE (CE23).pdf*)

Element Name	Min	PPM	Max	+/- [*3]
MgO	0	24386	0	9237
Al2O3	0	128976	0	3433
SiO2	0	521631	0	4085
P2O5	0	8920	0	387
S	0	2389	0	120
Cl	0	0	0	170
K2O	0	6982	0	127
CaO	0	156453	0	450
Ti	0	3841	0	60
V	0	45	0	22
Cr	0	122	0	19
Mn	0	308	0	74
Fe	0	24880	0	362
Co	0	0	0	20
Ni	0	21	0	21
Cu	0	1045	0	47
Zn	0	1226	0	39
As	0	2	0	12
Se	0	0	0	7
Rb	0	19	0	7
Sr	0	200	0	11
Y	0	22	0	9
Zr	0	180	0	9
Nb	0	0	0	7
Mo	0	7	0	9
Pd	0	0	0	27
Ag	0	8	0	17
Cd	0	0	0	25
Sn	0	0	0	94
Sb	0	0	0	35
Ba	0	634	0	201
La	0	0	0	472
Ce	0	0	0	90
Hf	0	3	0	59
Ta	0	0	0	20
W	0	15	0	20
Pt	0	0	0	24
Au	0	0	0	22
Hg	0	0	0	13
Tl	0	0	0	14
Pb	0	396	0	30
Bi	0	8	0	23
Th	0	0	0	30
U	0	0	0	64

AFTER testing (extracted from *Tabla hormigones.xlsx*)

Element Name	Min	PPM	Max	+/- [*3]
MgO	0	9511	0	6702
Al2O3	0	7223	0	1401
SiO2	0	0	0	720
P2O5	0	1107	0	265
S	0	0	0	143
Cl	0	664	0	39
K2O	0	0	0	93
CaO	0	165047	0	489
Ti	0	6954	0	106
V	0	79	0	50
Cr	0	112	0	34
Mn	0	417	0	79
Fe	0	56264	0	544
Co	0	0	0	130
Ni	0	74	0	23
Cu	0	440	0	26
Zn	0	725	0	27
As	0	6	0	5
Se	0	0	0	6
Rb	0	12	0	6
Sr	0	139	0	9
Y	0	33	0	9
Zr	0	115	0	7
Nb	0	12	0	10
Mo	0	6	0	8
Rh	0	0	0	15
Pd	0	0	0	29
Ag	0	0	0	13
Cd	0	0	0	21
Sn	0	623	0	285
Sb	0	0	0	30
Ba	0	253	0	117
La	0	0	0	239
Ce	0	0	0	221
Hf	0	0	0	55
Ta	0	0	0	10
W	0	5	0	16
Pt	0	6	0	32
Au	0	10	0	18
Hg	0	0	0	11
Tl	0	0	0	11
Pb	0	263	0	29
Bi	0	0	0	20
Th	0	0	0	26
U	0	0	0	62

HEATREK-RVBEFORE testing (extracted from *HEATEK-RV 1.pdf*)

Element Name	Min	PPM	Max	+/- [*3]
MgO	0	15503	0	12313
Al2O3	0	151078	0	4190
SiO2	0	113570	0	2213
P2O5	0	5386	0	410
S	0	994	0	137
Cl	0	0	0	163
K2O	0	0	0	97
CaO	0	273902	0	639
Ti	0	4980	0	91
V	0	682	0	47
Cr	0	11420	0	97
Mn	0	22900	0	445
Fe	0	193837	0	1134
Co	0	0	0	149
Ni	0	157	0	73
Cu	0	281	0	54
Zn	0	569	0	44
As	0	0	0	9
Se	0	0	0	14
Rb	0	0	0	13
Sr	0	435	0	24
Y	0	14	0	19
Zr	0	249	0	18
Nb	0	263	0	26
Mo	0	34	0	19
Rh	0	0	0	8
Pd	0	0	0	18
Ag	0	0	0	17
Cd	0	6	0	47
Sn	0	0	0	113
Sb	0	0	0	91
Ba	0	1827	0	320
La	0	0	0	127
Ce	0	0	0	262
Hf	0	0	0	30
Ta	0	0	0	25
W	0	72	0	37
Pt	0	0	0	17
Au	0	0	0	45
Hg	0	38	0	27
Tl	0	0	0	24
Pb	0	57	0	35
Bi	0	0	0	44
Th	0	0	0	59
U	0	0	0	133

(extracted from *Tabla hormigones.xlsx*)

Element Name	Min	PPM	Max	+/- [*3]
MgO	0	16778	0	14147
Al2O3	0	167196	0	4463
SiO2	0	115822	0	2251
P2O5	0	4869	0	403
S	0	794	0	147
Cl	0	1387	0	197
K2O	0	1124	0	108
CaO	0	260101	0	627
Ti	0	4953	0	91
V	0	608	0	47
Cr	0	13035	0	108
Mn	0	21080	0	427
Fe	0	243105	0	1262
Co	0	140	0	164
Ni	0	191	0	79
Cu	0	308	0	55
Zn	0	754	0	50
As	0	0	0	10
Se	0	0	0	14
Rb	0	0	0	14
Sr	0	331	0	23
Y	0	23	0	20
Zr	0	246	0	18
Nb	0	226	0	26
Mo	0	40	0	19
Rh	0	0	0	8
Pd	0	0	0	17
Ag	0	0	0	13
Cd	0	10	0	49
Sn	0	0	0	105
Sb	0	0	0	65
Ba	0	1809	0	316
La	0	0	0	3
Ce	0	0	0	274
Hf	0	0	0	28
Ta	0	0	0	25
W	0	60	0	40
Pt	0	0	0	18
Au	0	0	0	47
Hg	0	0	0	29
Tl	0	0	0	28
Pb	0	72	0	32
Bi	0	59	0	48
Th	0	0	0	60
U	0	0	0	140

AFTER testing (extracted from *Tabla hormigones.xlsx*)

Element Name	Min	PPM	Max	+/- [*3]
MgO	0	13200	0	9067
Al2O3	0	36945	0	2463
SiO2	0	51647	0	1597
P2O5	0	2304	0	313
S	0	0	0	147
Cl	0	0	0	83
K2O	0	16907	0	197
CaO	0	185533	0	529
Ti	0	4640	0	91
V	0	364	0	46
Cr	0	9299	0	84
Mn	0	15322	0	358
Fe	0	139788	0	897
Co	0	0	0	169
Ni	0	113	0	45
Cu	0	139	0	27
Zn	0	248	0	25
As	0	12	0	6
Se	0	0	0	10
Rb	0	213	0	15
Sr	0	368	0	19
Y	0	35	0	15
Zr	0	171	0	12
Nb	0	131	0	18
Mo	0	26	0	13
Rh	0	0	0	11
Pd	0	0	0	21
Ag	0	0	0	15
Cd	0	0	0	32
Sn	0	159	0	173
Sb	0	0	0	44
Ba	0	1234	0	202
La	0	0	0	194
Ce	0	0	0	273
Hf	0	0	0	30
Ta	0	0	0	28
W	0	31	0	23
Pt	0	0	0	19
Au	0	0	0	27
Hg	0	0	0	19
Tl	0	0	0	17
Pb	0	59	0	32
Bi	0	0	0	31
Th	0	0	0	43
U	0	54	0	92

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- 1 Boulet, N., et al. (2018). "MicroSol-R: Versatile solar facility for research and industry." AIP Conference Proceedings 2033(1): 030003. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5067019>
 - 2 Aslani, F. and Samali, B. (2013), "Constitutive relationships for steel fiber reinforced concrete at elevated temperatures", Fire Tech., doi: 10.1007/s10694-012-0322-5.
 - 3 Aslani, F. and Samali, B. (2013), "High strength polypropylene fibre reinforcement concrete at high temperature", Fire Tech., doi: 10.1007/s10694-013-0332-y
 - 4 Aslani, F. and Samali, B. (2013), "Constitutive relationships for self-compacting concrete at elevated temperatures", Mater. Struct., doi: 10.1617/s11527-013-0187-1.
 - 5 W.-. S. Gobain, "Arlita® Leca Solar Technical product datasheet," 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://www.weber.es/soluciones-ligeras-con-arlitareg-lecareg/soluciones/arlitareg-lecareg/arlitaregnbsplecareg-solar.html>.
 - 6 R. Lo Frano, D. Aquaro, S. Pupeschi and M. Moscar, "Thermo-mechanical test rig for experimental evaluation of thermal conductivity of ceramic pebble beds," Fusion Engineering and Design, no. 89, pp. 1309-1313, 2014.
 - 7 G. Widenfeld, Y. Weiss and H. Kalman, "The effect of compression and preconsolidation on the effective thermal conductivity of particulate beds," Powder technology, vol. 1, no. 133, pp. 15-22, 2003.
 - 8 A. Hoseini , A. Malekian and M. Bahrami., "Deformation and thermal resistance study of aerogel blanket insulation material under uniaxial compression," Energy and Buildings, no. 130, pp. 228-237, 2016.
 - 9 H. Bal, Y. Jannot, S. Gaye and F. Demeurie, "Measurement and modelisation of the thermal conductivity of a wet composite porous medium: Laterite based bricks with millet waste additive," Construction and Building Materials, no. 41, pp. 586-593, 2013.
 - 10 J. Florez, M. Mantelli and G. Nuern, "Effective thermal conductivity of sintered porous media: Model and experimental validation," International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer, no. 66, pp. 868-878, 2013.
 - 11 J. Reimann, G. Piazza and H. Harsch, "Thermal conductivity of compressed beryllium pebble beds.," Fusion Engineering and Design, vol. 1, no. 81, pp. 449-454, 2006